

The Implementation Of Akhlak Core Values On Work Behaviour At Ptpn Iv North Sumatra Province With Structural Equation Modelling

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Аннотация: This study aims to evaluate the effect of the implementation of AKHLAK Core Values (Amanah, Kompeten, Harmonious, Loyal, Adaptive, and Collaborative) on employee work behaviour at PT Perkebunan Nusantara IV (PTPN IV), North Sumatra Province. This study uses a quantitative approach with the SMARTPLS analysis method to test the relationship between latent variables. Data were collected through questionnaires filled out by PTPN IV employees. The results showed that the application of AKHLAK values has a positive and significant influence on employee work behaviour. The Amanah and Collaborative dimensions contribute the most in improving productivity, ethics, and cooperation in the work environment. Meanwhile, the Harmonious dimension requires more attention in managing relationships between employees, especially in dealing with conflict. The research model shows a good fit, with indicators that fulfil validity and reliability criteria. AKHLAK Core Values proved effective as a guide in creating a productive work culture and integrity within PTPN IV. Research recommendations include strengthening the socialisation of AKHLAK values, conflict management training, as well as ongoing evaluation to optimise the implementation of the AKHLAK Core Values in PTPN IV.

Ключевые слова: Implementation, Core Values AKHLAK, Work Behaviour, PTPN IV

1. Introduction

Human Resources (HR) are individuals who work in an organisation, covering all types of work, whether manual, professional or managerial. According to Gary Dessler, HR is an important element in the organisation because its contribution directly affects the success of the company. With this crucial role, HR becomes a strategic asset that must be maintained and developed in order to bring the organisation to a better direction. HR is a crucial asset in an organisation because they directly contribute to the performance and success of the company. Humans are the key element in an organisation which means they have a crucial function in every organisational activity. The role of humans is crucial to achieving development goals. So, HR is an asset or basic capital in an organisation that needs to be maintained and maintained its quality which makes it able to direct the organisation to a more positive path.[1]

As an important element in the economic structure, State-Owned Enterprises (SOEs) have a strategic responsibility not only in financial aspects but also in the establishment of an organisational culture that supports the implementation of core values. SOEs are established to support national economic growth, increase state revenue, provide quality

goods and services, and pioneer business activities that the private sector has not been able to undertake. In addition, SOEs also play a role in guiding cooperatives, small entrepreneurs, and communities, and pursue profits like private companies.[2].

For SOEs to grow sustainably in the era of globalisation, they need a strong corporate foundation with high competitiveness. One way to achieve this is by improving overall HR performance. This involves the development of personality, competence, experience and education that have a positive impact on work effectiveness. In addition, work behaviour, which reflects the achievement of organisational goals, is also an important focus.[3]

As part of the transformation of human resources, the Ministry of SOEs introduced the Core Values of AKHLAK-Amanah, Competent, Harmonious, Loyal, Adaptive, and Collaborative. These values guide the behaviour of all SOE employees to create a professional, integrity and productive work culture. The implementation of AKHLAK is expected to harmonise HR governance in various SOEs to support the achievement of national strategic goals.[2].

Performance development includes personality, experience, competence, and education, as well as behaviour modification and improvement techniques, which provide added value that allows a person to work better. The resources owned by the company will not provide optimal results if not supported by human resources who have optimal performance. Efforts to improve work behaviour include paying attention to the level of education. In addition, work experience is also needed by employees to improve employee performance.[4].

Work behaviour is a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of a policy in realising the goals, objectives, vision and mission of the organisation as stated in an organisational work plan.[3] In order to improve the work behaviour of SOEs, the Ministry of SOEs is implementing a priority implementation programme by launching a new value system in the form of AKHLAK Core Values as an effort to develop SOE human resources. The significant role of SOEs for the national economy but the high disparity in terms of management systems between SOEs, the Ministry of SOEs feels the need to transform and align HR guidelines in SOEs entitled "BUMN Human Capital Transformation", namely AKHLAK. The AKHLAK culture applied by SOEs stands for Amanah, Kompeten, Harmonious, Loyal, Adaptive and Collaborative, which are the Core Values of SOEs. AKHLAK BUMN is a behavioural guide for every human resource (HR) of BUMN to be implemented in daily behaviour and form a work culture in BUMN.[5].

AKHLAK culture at PT Perkebunan Nusantara IV will create a foundation of moral and ethical values that are applied in the entire organisational structure. Some aspects of the relationship between culture and Core Values AKHLAK at PT Perkebunan Nusantara IV include Morals and Ethics as the Foundation of Core Values AKHLAK, Increased Worker Engagement, Trust and Good Working Relations, the importance of shared values empowerment and recognition of positive impact and productivity. The positive relationship between culture and Core Value AKHLAK indicates that creating a work environment that focuses on moral values can be an important factor in improving employee engagement, motivation, and performance. The implementation of a good AKHLAK culture in an organisation can have a positive long-term impact on the growth and sustainability of the company.[6]

PT Perkebunan Nusantara IV North Sumatra Province as part of a national company and is a State-Owned Enterprise (BUMN) company must ensure that the AKHLAK culture that is applied is in accordance with the values upheld so that it can affect Core Values. Based on the results of preliminary observations that have been made, the author can see

that the Core Values of AKHLAK BUMN which include Amanah, Competent, Harmonious, Loyal, Adaptive and Collaborative have been implemented by the work behaviour of PT Perkebunan Nusantara IV North Sumatra Province in accordance with the indicators of each point.[7]

The role of PT Perkebunan Nusantara IV North Sumatra Province as a company engaged in the plantation sector requires Core Values and good employee performance so that it can survive and provide the best service to the community. Based on this, PT Perkebunan Nusantara IV North Sumatra Province is committed to continuing to make innovations and new breakthrough initiatives to support performance improvement, optimisation of services to the community in 2024 and by applying the Core Values of AKHLAK.[5]

2. Literature Review

Definition of Human Resource Management

Human resource management is a strategic process that includes recruitment, selection, development, maintenance, and management of the workforce to achieve organisational and individual goals. HR includes the management of individuals within the organisation, both small and large. Each individual is managed according to specific needs, so that HR development is flexible to support optimal performance.[8]

Implementation

Implementation refers to the application or realisation of plans, policies, or strategies into concrete actions to achieve the set goals.[9] In an organisational context, implementation involves concrete steps using resources such as manpower, technology, and budget. Work behaviour implementation focuses on applying patterns of employee actions, attitudes, and habits according to certain guidelines to improve productivity, efficiency, and professionalism. Similarly, work culture implementation aims to embed organisational values and principles in daily activities, creating a strong organisational identity.[10]

Roles and Functions of Human Resource Management

The roles and functions of HR according to viz:[11][12]

1. Planning: Developing workforce requirements to meet organisational objectives.
2. Organisation: Division of tasks, delegation of authority, and coordination within the organisational structure.
3. Direction: Provide direction to employees to work effectively and efficiently.
4. Control: Supervise the implementation of work according to established rules.
5. Procurement: Recruiting, selecting and placing individuals that meet the needs of the organisation.
6. Development: Improving the technical, conceptual, and moral capabilities of employees through education and training.
7. Compensation: Rewarding employees for their contributions in the form of salary or other forms.
8. Integration: Harmonising organisational interests and employee needs to create a productive working relationship.
9. Maintenance: Keeping employees in optimal physical, mental and loyal condition until retirement.

Definition of Core Values

Core values are the core principles that guide the behaviour and work culture of an organisation. These values are designed to reflect the identity of the organisation and ensure relevance and effective implementation in various work situations. In the context of SOEs, Core Values AKHLAK, acronym for Amanah, Kompeten, Harmonious, Loyal, Adaptive, and Collaborative, serve as a strategic guide to align work culture across the organisation.[13]

Core Value Formation Process

The AKHLAK core values were formulated as part of the Ministry of SOEs' strategic initiative to unify the work culture across state-owned enterprises. The process involved in-depth analysis, cross-company participation, and strategic policy direction. The AKHLAK values aim to:[14]

- Improving Integrity and Professionalism: The Trustworthy and Competent dimension supports work quality and trust.
- Forming Harmonious Cooperation: Harmonious and Collaborative dimensions strengthen inter-SOE synergies.[15]
- Enhancing Global Competitiveness: The Adaptive Dimension supports innovation and response to change.[16]
- Strengthening Loyalty to the Country: The Loyal dimension ensures orientation towards the interests of the nation.[17]

Performance

Performance refers to the results of an employee's work over a period of time, measured against agreed standards. These standards include goals, objectives or assessment criteria used to judge individual success. An organisation's performance is an accumulation of the success of its employees. When individual achievements exceed the standard, the employee is considered an achiever.[18] Organisational culture reflects the values, norms and assumptions shared by members of the organisation. Organisational culture approaches can be symbolic or functional to make it easier to implement and teach these values to new members.[19][20].

3. Methods

This study uses a quantitative approach with the SMARTPLS analysis method to test the relationship between latent variables. The number of employees sampled was 210 people, drawn using the purposive random sampling method. Data were collected through questionnaires filled out by PTPN IV employees.

4. Results And Discussion

SEM-PLS Analysis

In data analysis Structural Equation Modelling-Partial Least Structural (SEM-PLS) using SmartPLS software version 4. The PLS calculation stages use 2 models, namely Model Measurement (Outer Model) and Structural Model Testing (Inner Model).

Figure 2. Outer Model Structural Equation Modelling

The standards specified in this model specify the relationship between latent variables and their indicators or it can be said that the outer model defines how each indicator relates to its latent variable.

Convergent validity is part of the measurement model which in SEM-PLS is usually referred to as the outer model while in covariancebased SEM it is called confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) (Mahfud and Ratmono, 2013). There are two criteria for assessing whether the outer model (measurement model) meets the requirements of convergent validity for reflective constructs, namely (1) loading must be above 0.7 and (2) significant p value (<0.05). However, in some cases, the loading factor requirement above 0.7 is often not met, especially for newly developed questionnaires. Therefore, loading between 0.40-0.70 should still be considered to be maintained. The Validity Testing (loading factors) using smartPLS 4. for this study can be seen in table 1.

Table 1. Validity Test Loading Factor

	Moral Core Values (Y)	Habit (X ₂)	Performance (X ₃)	Work Behaviour (X ₁)
CV1	0.922			
CV10	0.765			
CV2	0.905			
CV3	0.873			
CV4	0.931			
CV5	0.905			
CV6	0.905			
CV7	0.900			
CV8	0.869			
CV9	0.864			
HA1		0.933		
HA10		0.929		
HA2		0.905		
HA3		0.932		
HA4		0.874		
HA5		0.875		
HA6		0.946		
HA7		0.927		

	Moral Core Values (Y)	Habit (X ₂)	Performance (X ₃)	Work Behaviour (X ₁)
HA8		0.872		
HA9		0.937		
PE1			0.948	
PE10			0.960	
PE2			0.926	
PE3			0.909	
PE4			0.943	
PE5			0.885	
PE6			0.952	
PE7			0.878	
PE8			0.892	
PE9			0.938	
PK1				0.900
PK10				0.880
PK2				0.934
PK3				0.944
PK4				0.930
PK5				0.964
PK6				0.937
PK7				0.914
PK8				0.964
PK9				0.922

Based on table 1, the results of validity testing using SmartPLS 4 show that the loading factor values of all question items > 0.50 and loading between > 0.40 are still considered to be maintained, so all question items are considered convergent valid.

Figure 3. Inner Model Structural Equation Modelling

Based on the outer loading validity test in Table 1 and Figure 2, it is known that all outer loading values are > 0.7, which means that they have met the validity requirements based on the outer loading value. Furthermore, validity testing is carried out based on the average variance extracted (AVE) value.

Hypothesis Test

Direct Effect

Table 2. Direct Path Coefficient Test

	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	t Statistics	p Values
Habit (X2) -> Core Values Akhlak (Y)	0.387	0.386	0.164	2.364	0.018
Performance (X3) -> Moral Core Values (Y)	0.408	0.395	0.145	2.823	0.005
Work Behaviour (X1) -> Moral Core Values (Y)	0.364	0.356	0.159	2.287	0.023

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS 4 (2024)

From table 2, analytical decisions can be made with consideration of the decision-making standards, so that each relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable through each intervening can be described as follows:

1. Habit (X2) has a positive effect on Moral Core Values (Y), with a coefficient value (Original Sample column) = 0.387, and is significant, with T-Statistics = 2.364 > 1.96 and P-Values = 0.018 < 0.05 (Hypothesis Accepted).
2. Performance (X3) has a positive effect on Moral Core Values (Y), with a coefficient value (Original Sample column) = 0.408, and significant, with T-Statistics = 2.823, and significant, with T-Statistics = 2.364 > 1.96 and P-Values = 0.005 < 0.05 (Hypothesis Accepted).
3. Work Behaviour (X1) has a positive effect on Moral Core Values (Y), with a coefficient value (Original Sample column) = 0.364, and significant, with T-Statistics = 2.287, and significant, with T-Statistics = 2.364 > 1.96 and P-Values = 0.023 < 0.05 (Hypothesis Accepted).

5. Conclusion

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that:

1. Habit (X2) has a positive effect on Moral Core Values (Y), with a coefficient value (Original Sample column) = 0.387, and is significant, with T-Statistics = 2.364 > 1.96 and P-Values = 0.018 < 0.05 (Hypothesis Accepted).
2. Performance (X3) has a positive effect on Moral Core Values (Y), with a coefficient value (Original Sample column) = 0.408, and significant, with T-Statistics = 2.823, and significant, with T-Statistics = 2.364 > 1.96 and P-Values = 0.005 < 0.05 (Hypothesis Accepted).
3. Work Behaviour (X1) has a positive effect on Moral Core Values (Y), with a coefficient value (Original Sample column) = 0.364, and significant, with T-Statistics = 2.287, and significant, with T-Statistics = 2.364 > 1.96 and P-Values = 0.023 < 0.05 (Hypothesis Accepted).

4. This study reveals that the implementation of AKHLAK Core Values in PTPN IV North Sumatra Province significantly affects the improvement of employee work behaviour. The dimensions of Amanah, Competent, and Harmonious provide the greatest contribution, while other dimensions require further strengthening. With a strategy that focuses on improving the implementation of AKHLAK consistently, PTPN IV can strengthen a work culture that is superior, productive, and adaptive to changes in the business environment.

5. Implementation of AKHLAK has a Significant Effect on Work Behaviour, Findings: The analysis shows that the implementation of AKHLAK core values has a significant and positive relationship with employee work behaviour. Explanation: AKHLAK dimensions, such as Amanah (integrity) and Kompeten (professionalism), directly influence proactive, responsible and result-oriented work behaviour.

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